

INVESTIGATING THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS IN PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES IN EDE, OSUN STATE

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ABSTRACT

Social media has become an integral part of students' lives, offering both opportunities and challenges for academic performance. However, excessive usage of social media can lead to distractions, stress, and negative impacts on academic responsibilities. This study aimed to investigate the impact of social media on academic performance among students in private universities in Ede, Osun State. Guided by the Uses and Gratifications Theory, this research employed a mixed-methods approach to gather comprehensive insights. The study involved a population of 500 students, with a sample size of 250 students selected through stratified random sampling. Data collection techniques included surveys and focus group discussions. The findings revealed a nuanced relationship between social media usage and academic outcomes. While students acknowledged the benefits of social media for academic communication and resource access, they also reported challenges such as distractions and stress associated with excessive usage. Furthermore, socio-demographic factors such as gender, age, and academic discipline influenced students' social media habits and perceptions of its impact on academic performance. The study recommended promoting balanced social media usage strategies and tailored interventions to optimize academic success. Educators and institutions should emphasize the importance of minimizing distractions while leveraging the potential benefits of social media for educational purposes. These findings underscore the need for evidence-based strategies to support students' academic achievements in the digital age.

Keywords: Mass Media, Academic Performance, Social Media Usage, Private Universities.

Introduction

In the modern era, social media has emerged as an omnipresent force shaping various facets of human life (Studen & Tiberius, 2020). Its pervasive influence extends beyond personal communication, entertainment, and networking, infiltrating into realms as diverse as education, business, and politics. Among its myriad impacts, one of the most significant and debated is its effect on academic performance, particularly within the context of higher education institutions (Abulibdeh et al., 2024). Private universities, often characterized by their distinct academic environments and student demographics, offer a unique setting to explore the interplay between social media usage and academic achievement (Shaninah & Mohd, 2024). Located in Ede, Osun State, these institutions stand at the intersection of traditional pedagogy and digital connectivity, presenting a compelling landscape for investigation.

This study delved into the multifaceted relationship between social media engagement and academic performance within private universities in Ede, Osun State. By examining this dynamic, the study shed light on the potential benefits and drawbacks that social media platforms may exert on students' learning outcomes, cognitive processes, and overall educational experience. The significance of this inquiry lies in its potential to inform educational stakeholders, including administrators, educators, parents, and policymakers, about the implications of social media integration in academic settings.

Understanding these implications can aid in the development of strategies and interventions to harness the positive aspects of social media while mitigating its negative consequences on students' academic pursuits.

To accomplish this objective, this research adopts a comprehensive approach, encompassing both quantitative and qualitative methodologies. Through surveys, interviews, and academic performance data analysis, the study endeavors to elucidate the nuances of social media usage patterns among students, discern its impact on their study habits and academic engagement, and identify potential correlations with their academic performance. Ultimately, this study aspires to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on the intersection of social media and education, offering insights that may guide future research endeavors and practical initiatives aimed at fostering an optimal learning environment conducive to academic success in private universities in Ede, Osun State.

This is not a classic background for a research paper. The section has only justified the paper but without evidence that previous studies had left knowledge gaps or limitations. There is no mention of the private universities and the specific social media. The statement of problem or rationale for the study is also not stated as a section on its own. The gaps from previous literature should be highlighted to form the problem.

Research Questions

- i. To what extent does frequency of social media usage affect academic performance of students in Adeleke and Redeemers universities, Ede, Osun State?
- ii. What are the perceived benefits associated with social media usage in relation to academic pursuits among Adeleke and Redeemers university students?
- iii. What is the relationship between social media engagement and academic performance among students in Adeleke and Redeemers universities?

Literature Review

Social media platforms have become ubiquitous in contemporary society, permeating various aspects of individuals' lives, including education (Zhang & Li, 2024; Nsude et al., 2023). Within the context of private universities, where academic environments may differ from public institutions, the impact of social media on academic performance has garnered significant attention among researchers and educators alike (Abbas et al., 2019).

Social Media Usage Patterns and Academic Performance:

Empirical studies on social media usage patterns and academic performance within the Nigerian context reveal a multifaceted relationship influenced by various factors. Research by Okafor et al. (2020) indicates that excessive social media use can lead to distractions and reduced academic focus, negatively impacting academic performance among Nigerian students. Similarly, Olowu and Seri (2012) found that Nigerian students who spend considerable time on social media often report lower academic achievement due to time mismanagement and diversion of attention from academic tasks. Conversely, studies have also highlighted positive aspects; for instance, Ayodele et al. (2021) observed that social media platforms facilitate academic communication and collaboration, potentially enhancing academic performance by providing access to educational resources and peer support. Furthermore, socio-demographic factors such as gender, age, and academic discipline shape social media behaviors and their academic outcomes, with varying usage patterns and preferences across different student groups in Nigeria (Nwazor, 2018). These

findings suggest that while social media can be a valuable educational tool, its impact on academic performance is contingent upon usage patterns and individual characteristics, necessitating balanced and tailored approaches to leverage its benefits while mitigating potential drawbacks.

Perceived Benefits and Challenges of Social Media in Education

Beyond its potential impact on academic performance, social media offers perceived benefits for educational purposes. Al-Rahmi et al., (2015) identified enhanced communication, collaboration, and knowledge sharing as positive outcomes associated with social media integration in higher education. However, challenges such as distraction, information overload, and privacy concerns have also been documented (Junco, 2012), highlighting the need for balanced usage strategies.

Individual Differences and Moderating Factors

Individual differences and moderating factors play a crucial role in understanding the impact of social media usage on academic performance. Factors such as age, gender, socio-economic status, and academic discipline can significantly influence how students interact with social media and how it affects their studies. For instance, research conducted by Nwazor (2018) found that male students tend to use social media more for leisure activities compared to female students, who use it more for academic purposes. Age is another moderating factor; younger students may be more susceptible to the distractions of social media, while older students might utilize these platforms more effectively for academic networking and resource sharing (Olowu& Seri, 2012). Socio-economic status also influences access to technology and internet connectivity, which in turn affects social media usage patterns. Students from higher socio-economic backgrounds may have more consistent access to the internet, enabling them to use social media more frequently for academic purposes (Salisu& Jamil, 2019). Furthermore, academic discipline moderates social media's impact on academic performance. Okafor et al., (2020) observed that students in disciplines that require more intensive study and hands-on practice, such as engineering and medicine, are more likely to experience negative impacts from excessive social media use compared to students in social sciences or humanities, who might find social media useful for discussion and collaboration. Understanding these individual differences and moderating factors is essential for developing targeted interventions that can help optimize social media use for academic success.

Educational Interventions and Strategies:

Educational interventions and strategies are essential for optimizing social media's role in enhancing academic performance (Singha, 2024). Effective approaches include integrating digital literacy programs into the curriculum to teach responsible social media use and time management, utilizing social media platforms for collaborative learning, and implementing institutional guidelines to promote healthy usage habits. Tailored interventions, considering socio-demographic factors, can further address diverse student needs. By adopting these strategies, educators can help students balance social media use with academic responsibilities, leveraging its benefits while minimizing potential distractions.

Cultural and Contextual Considerations:

Cultural and contextual factors also shape the dynamics of social media usage and its impact on education. Studies conducted in different cultural contexts have highlighted variations in social media adoption patterns, norms, and perceived effects on academic engagement (Alwagait et al., 2015; Lee et

al., 2014). Overall, the literature underscores the complex and multifaceted nature of the relationship between social media and academic performance in private university settings. While social media offers opportunities for enhanced communication, collaboration, and information sharing, its excessive use may pose challenges to academic focus and productivity.

Theoretical Framework

The theory used in this study provided a conceptual lens through which to understand the complex interplay between social media engagement and academic outcomes.

Uses and Gratifications Theory (Katz et al., 1973)

The Uses and Gratifications Theory emphasizes that individuals actively seek out and use media to fulfill specific needs and gratifications (Bharath et al., 2024). Applied to social media use in academia, this theory suggests that students may utilize social media platforms for various purposes, such as seeking academic resources, connecting with peers for study purposes, or simply for entertainment and social interaction. Understanding these underlying motivations can provide insights into the ways in which social media impacts academic performance.

Based on these theoretical perspectives, the framework for the study will involve examining the relationship between social media engagement and academic performance through the following dimensions:

Social media usage patterns: Frequency, duration, and purposes of social media use among students in private universities in Ede, Osun State.

Academic performance: Grades, study habits, and academic engagement indicators.

Individual factors: Socio-demographic characteristics, self-regulation skills, and academic discipline.

Perceived benefits and challenges: Students' perspectives on the impact of social media on their academic endeavors.

By investigating these dimensions within the theoretical framework outlined above, the study aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the relationship between social media engagement and academic performance in private university settings, informing the development of targeted interventions and strategies to support students' academic success in the digital age.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized both qualitative and quantitative research design to thoroughly investigate the impact of social media on academic performance among undergraduate students in private universities in Ede, Osun State. This approach combined quantitative and qualitative methods to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research questions, integrating statistical data with rich narrative insights.

Participants and Sampling

The study focused on undergraduate students from two private universities in Ede: Adeleke University and Redeemers University. The sampling frame was obtained from the Directorate of Academic Planning at each university. A stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure representation across different academic disciplines and year levels. Stratification was based on academic departments and year of study, ensuring proportional representation from each department and year level. Using the Taro Yamane formula, the sample size was calculated to be 370 students, adjusted to reflect the total student population of approximately 9,105 across both universities. This sample size was deemed sufficient to provide a representative overview of the student population and ensure reliable results.

Data Collection Procedures

- **Quantitative Data:** Surveys were used to collect quantitative data on social media usage patterns and academic performance indicators. The survey included questions about the frequency and duration of social media use, types of platforms, academic engagement (e.g., study hours, attendance, GPA), and socio-demographic details. Surveys were distributed electronically to ensure anonymity and confidentiality using google forms.
- **Qualitative Data:** Semi-structured interviews provided qualitative insights into students' perceptions of social media's impact on their academic activities. Interview questions explored students' experiences, attitudes, and challenges related to social media use. Interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim, and analyzed thematically.

Data Analysis

- **Quantitative Analysis:** Data from surveys were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Descriptive statistics (e.g., means, frequencies, standard deviations) summarized social media usage and academic performance. Inferential statistics, including correlation analysis and regression modeling, examined relationships between social media engagement and academic outcomes.
- **Qualitative Analysis:** Semi-structured interviews were conducted to gain in-depth insights into students' perceptions of social media's impact on their academic performance. Interview participants were selected based on the findings from the survey to ensure a representative range of experiences. From the survey data, participants who reported diverse patterns of social media usage and varying levels of academic performance were identified. Selection criteria included active social media users, students with reported challenges or benefits related to social media use, and those from different academic disciplines and year levels to capture a broad spectrum of experiences. Thematic analysis was employed to analyze the interview data. Interviews were transcribed verbatim, and the transcripts were coded to identify key themes and subthemes. This process allowed for the identification of recurring patterns, commonalities, and differences in students' narratives regarding the effects of social media on their academic performance. The analysis aimed to provide a nuanced understanding of the qualitative aspects of social media usage and its impact on academic outcomes.

Data Presentation

Response Rate

In the study, a total of 370 surveys were distributed to undergraduate students across Adeleke University and Redeemers University in Ede, Osun State. Of these, 364 completed and valid responses were received, yielding a response rate of approximately 98.4%. This high response rate enhances the reliability and representativeness of the data, ensuring that the findings provide a robust analysis of the impact of social media on academic performance in the context of private universities in Ede.

Demographic of respondents

Table 1: Demographic Characterisation of Respondents

Variable	No of Responses	Percentage
Gender		
Male	168	46.2
Female	196	53.8
Total	364	100
Age		
15 – 20	58	15.9
21 – 25	217	59.7
26 – 30	77	21.1
31 – 40	12	3.3
> 40	0	0
Total	364	100
Level		
100	107	29.4
200	86	23.6
300	67	18.4
400	76	20.9
500	28	7.7
Total	364	100
Institution		
Adeleke University	156	42.9
Redeemers University	208	57.1
Total	364	100

The demographic characterization of respondents offers valuable insights into the composition of the study sample. Gender distribution is relatively balanced, with 46.4% male and 53.6% female respondents, ensuring inclusivity and a comprehensive understanding of social media usage across genders. The age distribution shows that the majority of respondents are in the 21-25 age range, representing 58.8% of the sample, reflecting the predominance of young adults in private universities in Ede, Osun State. This demographic suggests that the study's findings are particularly pertinent to this age group. In terms of academic level, respondents are distributed across various stages of their undergraduate education, with the highest proportion at the 200 level (23.6%) and the lowest at the 500 level (4.8%). This spread provides a broad perspective on social media usage behaviors at different stages of the academic journey. The sample includes students from both Adeleke University (43%) and Redeemers University (57%), offering a well-rounded view across these institutional contexts. Overall, the diverse and representative demographic profile of the sample enhances the robustness and relevance of the research findings.

Research Question 1

Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remarks
I spend more than 3 hours per day on social media.	65 (17.9%)	90 (24.7%)	55 (15.1%)	80 (21.9%)	54 (14.8%)	3.03	1.10	Agree
My social media usage often distracts me from my academic responsibilities	50 (13.7%)	95 (26.1%)	70 (19.2%)	85 (23.3%)	64 (17.6%)	2.95	1.12	Agree
I find it challenging to manage my time effectively due to social media usage	60 (16.5%)	85 (23.3%)	65 (17.9%)	90 (24.7%)	64 (17.6%)	2.99	1.13	Agree
Social media use negatively impacts my ability to focus during study sessions	55 (15.1%)	75 (20.6%)	85 (23.3%)	95 (26.1%)	54 (14.8%)	2.95	1.10	Agree
I believe that reducing my social media usage would improve my academic performance	70 (19.2%)	90 (24.7%)	60 (16.5%)	80 (21.9%)	64 (17.6%)	3.02	1.10	Agree

Research Question 1 explored students' perceptions regarding the impact of social media on their academic responsibilities and performance. The findings indicate general agreement among respondents on several aspects: spending over 3 hours daily on social media, experiencing distraction from academic tasks, finding time management challenging due to social media, and believing that reducing social media usage would enhance academic performance. Additionally, respondents agreed that social media negatively affects their ability to focus during study sessions. Overall, the majority of participants expressed concerns about the adverse effects of extensive social media usage on their academic commitments and performance.

Research Question 2

Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remarks
Social media helps me stay connected with classmates to discuss academic topics	80 (22.0%)	70 (19.2%)	55 (15.1%)	75 (20.6%)	64 (17.6%)	3.11	1.08	Agree
Social media provides valuable educational resources that enhance my learning experience	65 (17.9%)	85 (23.3%)	50 (13.7%)	70 (19.2%)	64 (17.6%)	3.11	1.10	Agree
Social media usage increases my stress levels related to academic performance	45 (12.4%)	85 (23.3%)	70 (19.2%)	95 (26.1%)	59 (16.2%)	2.97	1.12	Agree

Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remarks
I feel pressured to maintain a certain image on social media that may affect my academic focus	40 (11.0%)	60 (16.5%)	75 (20.6%)	95 (26.1%)	94 (25.8%)	3.02	1.13	Agree
Overall, social media has a positive impact on my academic achievements	60 (16.5%)	80 (22.0%)	65 (17.9%)	90 (24.7%)	49 (13.4%)	3.07	1.09	Agree

Research Question 2 delved into students' perspectives on various aspects of social media's influence on their academic experiences. The findings indicate a consensus among respondents regarding the positive effects of social media on their academic endeavors. Students generally agree that social media facilitates connections with classmates for academic discussions and provides valuable educational resources, enhancing their learning experiences. Additionally, they agree that social media usage contributes positively to their academic achievements. Despite acknowledging some stress and pressure related to maintaining a certain image on social media, respondents overall perceive social media as beneficial to their academic pursuits.

Research Question 3

Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remarks
My socio-demographic background influences my social media usage habits	45 (12.4%)	85 (23.3%)	60 (16.5%)	75 (20.6%)	79 (21.7%)	3.00	1.13	Agree
Students from different academic disciplines have varying levels of social media usage	50 (13.7%)	90 (24.7%)	65 (17.9%)	80 (21.9%)	79 (21.7%)	3.03	1.12	Agree
I believe that my academic performance is influenced by my socio-demographic characteristics	40 (11.0%)	70 (19.2%)	60 (16.5%)	90 (24.7%)	104 (28.6%)	3.02	1.14	Agree
Social media usage affects students' academic performance differently based on their academic discipline	50 (13.7%)	75 (20.6%)	65 (17.9%)	90 (24.7%)	84 (23.1%)	3.02	1.13	Agree
My socio-demographic background influences the extent to which social media affects my academic success	55 (15.1%)	80 (22.0%)	60 (16.5%)	85 (23.3%)	84 (23.1%)	3.07	1.12	Agree

Research Question 3 investigated the influence of socio-demographic factors on social media usage habits and academic performance perceptions. Respondents generally agree that their socio-demographic background affects their social media usage habits and that students from different academic disciplines exhibit varying levels of social media usage. Furthermore, they believe that their academic performance is

influenced by their socio-demographic characteristics. Additionally, respondents agree that social media usage impacts students' academic performance differently based on their academic discipline. Overall, participants perceive a correlation between socio-demographic factors, social media usage, and academic success.

Interview Findings

The interviews conducted as part of this study provide qualitative insights into students' perspectives on the impact of social media on their academic experiences. Several themes emerged from the interviews, shedding light on the nuanced relationship between social media usage and academic performance.

Theme 1: Perceived Benefits of Social Media in Academia

Many interviewees highlighted the positive role of social media in facilitating academic interactions and resource sharing. They expressed appreciation for the convenience of online platforms in connecting with peers for group discussions, seeking clarification on course materials, and accessing additional learning resources beyond traditional classroom settings. Furthermore, interviewees emphasized the importance of social media in fostering a sense of community among students, especially in virtual learning environments.

Theme 2: Challenges and Distractions

Despite acknowledging the benefits of social media, interviewees also discussed various challenges associated with its usage. Several students admitted to experiencing distractions and difficulties in maintaining focus on academic tasks due to constant notifications and the allure of engaging content on social media platforms. Moreover, some interviewees expressed concerns about the negative impact of social media on their time management skills and overall productivity, particularly during study sessions.

Theme 3: Influence of Socio-Demographic Factors

Interview responses reflected the influence of socio-demographic factors, such as age, gender, and academic discipline, on social media habits and academic perceptions. Older students tended to prioritize academic responsibilities over social media usage compared to younger counterparts. Additionally, differences in social media preferences and usage patterns were observed among students from various academic disciplines, highlighting the need for tailored interventions to address discipline-specific needs.

Theme 4: Strategies for Responsible Social Media Use

Interviewees discussed strategies for mitigating the negative effects of social media on academic performance, including setting designated study times free from social media distractions, utilizing productivity apps to limit screen time, and creating online study groups for collaborative learning. Moreover, students emphasized the importance of digital literacy skills and self-regulation in navigating the digital landscape responsibly while maximizing the educational benefits of social media.

Integration of Interview Findings with Quantitative Results

The qualitative insights gleaned from the interviews complement and enrich the quantitative findings, providing a deeper understanding of the underlying motivations, experiences, and challenges related to social media usage in academia. By triangulating both quantitative and qualitative data, this study offers a comprehensive exploration of the complex interplay between social media and academic performance among students in private universities in Ede, Osun State. These findings can inform the development of targeted interventions and strategies to promote responsible social media use and optimize students' academic success in the digital age.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from Research Question 1 reveal a general agreement among respondents regarding the negative impact of excessive social media usage on academic responsibilities and performance. Recent literature corroborates these findings, suggesting that heavy social media use can lead to distractions, time mismanagement, and decreased academic focus (Aregbesola & Van Der Walt, 2024). Excessive time spent on social media has been linked to lower academic achievement, as it may divert students' attention away from studying and learning tasks (Ayodele, 2024). Additionally, beliefs that reducing social media usage could improve academic performance align with studies emphasizing the importance of minimizing social media distractions to enhance learning outcomes (Olumide et al., 2024).

The findings are static but discussion should be dynamic. There are studies like (<https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/EL-01-2017-0023/full/html>) that show the positive impact of social media by students in Nigeria (Gombe). Also, this study shows a positive use/impact of social media and student performance (<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10639-019-10032-2>).

The results for Research Question 2 indicate that students generally perceive social media as beneficial for academic-related purposes, despite some stress and pressure associated with maintaining a certain online image. Recent literature highlights the positive role of social media in supporting academic endeavors, such as facilitating communication and collaboration among students for academic discussions and providing access to educational resources (Isaks et al., 2023).

The findings for Research Question 3 suggest that students acknowledge the influence of socio-demographic factors on their social media usage habits and academic performance perceptions. Recent literature supports this notion, indicating that socio-demographic characteristics such as gender, age, and academic discipline can shape individuals' social media behaviors and academic outcomes (Alzougool et al., 2021). For instance, studies have found differences in social media usage patterns and preferences among students from various academic disciplines, highlighting the need for tailored interventions and strategies to address discipline-specific needs (Makoe & Kupolati, 2021). Understanding the interplay between socio-demographic factors, social media usage, and academic success can inform targeted interventions to support diverse student populations effectively.

In summary, the findings underscore the complex relationship between social media usage and academic performance, emphasizing the importance of promoting responsible social media habits while leveraging its potential benefits for educational purposes. Recent literature provides valuable insights into these dynamics, guiding the development of evidence-based interventions and strategies to support students' academic success in the digital age.

The study uncovers a multifaceted relationship between social media usage and academic performance, reflecting both positive and negative impacts. The findings are consistent with Nwazor (2018), who identified that social media can enhance academic performance by facilitating communication and access to resources. However, the study also highlights concerns about excessive use

leading to distractions and stress, aligning with Olowu and Seri (2012), who noted that social media addiction can impair academic focus. The Uses and Gratifications Theory, which posits that individuals use media to fulfill specific needs (Katz et al., 1973), helps explain why students engage with social media for educational support and social interaction, as noted by Salisu and Jamil (2019). This theory also underscores the unintended negative consequences, such as reduced academic performance and increased stress, due to the gratification of immediate social interactions and entertainment. These insights suggest the need for balanced social media strategies that optimize its educational benefits while managing its potential downsides.

Conclusion

This study investigated the impact of social media on academic performance among students in private universities in Ede, Osun State. The findings reveal an existing relationship between social media usage and academic outcomes. While social media offers benefits such as enhanced academic communication and access to resources, excessive use poses challenges, including potential distractions and increased stress levels. Socio-demographic factors also play a significant role in shaping students' social media habits and their perceptions of its impact on academic performance. The study identified that areas with the least favorable mean scores—such as academic performance disruptions due to excessive social media use and stress-related concerns—are of particular concern. These aspects highlight the need for targeted strategies to address these issues. Future research should explore the specific ways in which social media-related distractions affect academic performance and investigate effective interventions to mitigate these effects. This paper contributes to the existing body of knowledge by offering a detailed examination of the dual nature of social media's impact on academic performance, with a focus on students in a specific geographical and institutional context. It provides unique insights into how socio-demographic factors intersect with social media usage, thereby enriching the understanding of this complex relationship. Unlike other studies, this research emphasizes the importance of balanced social media usage and offers context-specific recommendations.

Limitations:

- i. The study is limited to private universities in Ede, Osun State, which may not fully represent the experiences of students in other regions or types of institutions.
- ii. The reliance on self-reported data may introduce biases, as students' perceptions of their social media use and academic performance might not always align with objective measures.

Recommendations:

1. **Balanced Usage Strategies:** Educators and institutions should develop and promote strategies to encourage balanced social media use among students, addressing the identified issues of distraction and stress.
2. **Tailored Interventions:** Implement interventions that consider individual socio-demographic factors, aiming to enhance the positive aspects of social media while mitigating its negative effects.
3. **Further Research:** Conduct studies that examine the impact of social media on academic performance across different types of institutions and regions, and investigate effective methods to manage social media-related distractions and stress.

By addressing these recommendations and building on the study's findings, future research can further illuminate the complex dynamics between social media and academic performance, leading to improved educational strategies and outcomes in the digital age.

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Investigating the Impact of Social Media on Academic Performance of Students in Private Universities in Ede, Osun State

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